

CHARACTERISTICS OF USING INTERACTIVE METHODS IN INFORMATION-LIBRARY INSTITUTIONS OF THE EDUCATIONAL SYSTEM

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Annotation. In given clauses is spoken about search of new methods, ways and modes of work with the readers, improving knowledge and pedagogical skill of the librarians for increase of a learning efficiency

Key words: the librarian, school library, increase of readership, job with the readers, professional skill, information – resource centre.

Any conscious activity of a person is based on the extent to which he acquired the information he had previously acquired. As a person's practical and professional skills depend on the level of acquiring information about activities, the final result of the knowledge of the librarian also determines the reading level of the student.

Humanization of the educational process is of particular importance in the development of the current educational system. In general, humanization, democratization and liberalization of activities and relations Changes in the continuing education system require the creation of necessary conditions to satisfy the reader's needs for information. Also, the decree of the head of our state dated September 13, 2017 "On the program of comprehensive measures to develop the system of publication and distribution of book products, increase and promote the culture of reading and reading" is important in the continuation of the stage.

Books are the main source of knowledge and education for children. Reading is inextricably linked with the educational process at school, because children are introduced to the art of regular reading at school. At this point, it depends on the student's acquisition of academic subjects, mastering knowledge and independent work at school, and this process is entrusted to libraries [2, 4-p] manner towards him, needs, interests, personal qualities, talents, and internal capabilities should be used as a goal. In this process, the librarian conducts spiritual and educational work in a creative environment in subject-subject cooperation and achieves the expected efficiency.

The place and role of the modern librarian is in his searchability, self-awareness, and implementation of the "process" using all his skills [1.54-p.]. The librarian should realize that he is the designer of educational technology and should follow others in this direction. As an important center of formation of the idea of national independence in the minds of students, the After all, the library serves as an audience for students to

strengthen and expand their knowledge after class. In recent years, the issue of book reading among young people has become urgent.

Today, students are able to get a lot of information that is interesting for them, mainly from mass media and Internet sites. This is a positive phenomenon, of course. But as a result of such action, most of the students become indifferent to reading books education school libraries is also important. This requires the need to regularly conduct scientific research and research in this direction [3,58-p]. As a result of our observations, it became clear that the level of reading of fiction books by students is not satisfactory.

All the information coming through various media cannot serve to raise the moral level and culture of the student. Searching for effective ways to eliminate deficiencies in the student's activity in order to achieve the intended goal of increasing reading due to the high level of confidence in the reader, a mature level of communication culture, the superiority of the student's rejection of coercion and, on the contrary, their encouragement necessary. For this, the librarians themselves need to improve their knowledge and pedagogical skills and continuously search for new methods, tools and ways of working with the reader. It depends on the activity and attitude of the librarian, his desire for new things, his search for new things, his ability to include them in the process of working with the reader, and his motivation [1,91-p].

Being aware of changes in the field of education, news and their practical application, having electronic versions of textbooks, programs and manuals, and other necessary literature are certainly spiritual and educational activities. serves to ensure efficiency and increase the quality of education.

The non-traditional event called "Data base" held with readers in information-library institutions in order to introduce them to the news, social-political events, spiritual-educational news of our Republic is of particular importance in increasing reading. In the organization of the "Data Base" event, it is necessary to rely on specific events or social-political, economic, scientific and cultural news in the republic, and to take into account the age characteristics of students. Newspapers, magazines, Internet information and students' knowledge acquired during the lesson can be the main source for the conversation during the event. This information should be evidence-based and interesting. When preparing materials for the interview, questions on the topic should be prepared in advance for the readers. The fact that some of the questions are evidence-based and some are opinion-oriented will encourage readers to think logically, articulate their arguments, and be active.

During the "Data Base" event, the students' positive attitude towards the book will be further strengthened through questions such as what other information they have on the subject, where to get sources. Such events will be held on topics such as "What is the digital economy?", "Globalization process and ecology", "Education and youth",

"Internet: what is good and what is bad?", "New Uzbekistan to the top". fit for purpose. Students collect information with the help of a librarian and convey information to the participants in an interesting way through exhibitions of pictures and posters, books and timed press publications, as well as videos, video films and slides. Through such interactive activities, librarians help students improve their ability to search, learn and analyze information, gain research skills and experience, communication skills through participation in activities, and self-management, they achieve the formation of qualities such as activity, cooperation, responsiveness, and curiosity.

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